

change in the vapour pressure-temperature curve occurs as the supersaturated region is approached. This further confirms the deductions based on the study of viscosity, freezing point and electrical conductivity data. With only one or two exceptions, the curve $(\log p - 1/T)$ is a straight line. Hence, it appears that Clausius-Clapeyron equation is fairly applicable to these systems. The apparent anomaly in the case of sodium acetate may be due to its tendency to form several hydrates. Similar sort of behaviour is exhibited in $(\log \eta - 1/T)$ curves (Ram Gopal, Ph. D. thesis, 1946, Lucknow University).

In Table I the latent heats of evaporation from solutions and the constant C have been calculated. The value of the constant C is almost the same in every case. The values of the latent heat of evaporation can be divided in two categories

(a) Above 10,450 cal./g. mol. (b) Below 10,450 cal./g. mol.

Substances of category (a) show a marked tendency of forming solvates. Greater solvation will require greater shearing stress, and hence latent heat of evaporation will be greater than that in other cases. This tendency of forming hydrates is responsible for the departure from linearity in the above case. Thus, the departure is most marked in the case of sodium acetate, which has the highest tendency of forming solvates and consequently the highest latent heat of evaporation should be observed in this case. The lower values in category (b) may be due to depolymerisation of water molecules.

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THE RATE OF CRYSTAL GROWTH IN SUPERSATURATED SOLUTIONS. PART I

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The rate of crystal growth in supersaturated aqueous solutions of four substances have been measured at different temperatures. It is found that there exists a temperature at which the rate of growth is maximum.

The rate of crystal growth in melts has been studied by Tamman and his co-workers in detail (Tamman, "Kristallisieren und Schmelzen", p. 131). Walton and his co-workers have studied the speed of crystallisation of water and the effect of dissolved substances on this speed (Walton and Brann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 317; 1918, 40, 1168). It has been observed by these workers that for under-cooled melts, the rate of crystal growth increases with the degree of supercooling until at a certain temperature it reaches a maximum. On cooling further, the rate of crystal growth again decreases. It appears from a survey of literature that very little work has been done

on the growth of crystal from supersaturated solutions ("Crystal Growth", *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, April, 1949, p. 62). Hence the following work has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental procedure was similar to that adopted by Walton and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). A pyrex tube, one metre in length, closed at one end, was enclosed in a glass jacket, through which water at a desired temperature could be passed by means of Davies constant-temperature-water-supplier. The temperature of inflowing water was recorded by two thermometers placed 20 cm. apart. The mean of the two temperatures, which did not differ by more than half a degree, was taken to be the temperature of the jacket. The inner tube contained the supersaturated solution of the substance to be investigated. Crystallisation was induced by freshly prepared seed crystals. As soon as crystallisation started, the time taken by the crystal boundary to traverse a known distance was noted. The values were found to be repeatable. The rate of growth was determined at various temperatures. Ice-cold water was circulated for producing temperatures below the room temperature.

TABLE I

T_s , the saturation temperature in all cases was 40° ; only in the case of NH_4NO_3 it was 45° .

T.	Rate of crystal growth (in cm./min.) of			
	Na-acetate.	K-acetate.	Am. nitrate.	K-nitrate.
40.0°	...	...	0.7	...
38.0°	...	...	1.9	...
37.0°	0.7	...	3.4	...
35.0°	1.3	...	...	0.5
34.0°	...	...	4.1	0.8
32.5°	2.3	...	...	1.0*
31.0°	...	1.2	...	...
30.0°	3.3	...	...	...
27.5°	4.0	2.5	...	...
25.0°	4.7	3.2	...	...
22.5°	4.7	...	...	...
20.0°	4.8	5.7	...	...
17.5°	4.9	6.0	...	...
15.0°	5.2	...	...	...
13.5°	...	6.0	...	...
8.0°	3.9	6.1	...	...
4.0°	3.6	5.7	...	...

* Spontaneous crystallisation occurred.

DISCUSSION

From the results given in the above table, it can be easily seen that the rate of crystal growth passes through a maximum only in the case of sodium and potassium acetates, substances which produce highly supersaturated solutions, whereas in the case of potassium nitrate and ammonium nitrate, there appears to be no maximum in the speed of crystallisation. This may probably be due to the fact that the supersaturated solutions of sodium and potassium acetates are comparatively stable while the supersaturated solution of ammonium nitrate and potassium nitrate are unstable. Former solutions can be considerably under-cooled before spontaneous crystallisation can take place. While in the latter, spontaneous crystallisation occurs before the temperature of maximum rate of growth is reached. Increase in the rate of crystal growth has been observed in the case of KNO_3 and NH_4NO_3 with the supercooling. This confirms that these solutions were tending towards the region of maximum rate but spontaneous crystallisation occurred before the region was reached. Hence the maximum rate could not be observed in this case.

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